

ILLUMINATION OF YOUTH PSYCHOLOGY IN WORKS

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Abstract. The article presents a socio-psychological analysis of youth as an age group. The historical and social context of the formation of the key characteristics of youth as an age group is considered. The lifestyle and psychological characteristics of young people are described, the specifics of the place and functions of young people in the system of social relations are revealed. Achieving adulthood is defined as the main task of youth. Modern views on the problem of growing up are discussed.

Keywords: youth, age group, adulthood, youth, youth subculture, historical and cultural analysis.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern scientific space, young people as a social group traditionally attract increased attention. Youth issues are the subject of discussion in philosophy, sociology, psychology, pedagogy, and social work. Being a fairly large socio-demographic group, youth occupies an important place in the national economy, in production and is, in fact, the main source of replenishment of labor resources. Possessing creative abilities, being at the stage of development of physical, mental and social qualities, young people are one of the bearers of the intellectual potential of society and have a great social and professional perspective. It is able to acquire new knowledge, professions and specialties faster than other social groups in society.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As the most well-known definitions (including at the present time), two can be cited. One of them was given by V.T. Lisovsky: "Young people are a generation of people passing through the stage of socialization, assimilating, and at an older age already assimilating, educational, professional, cultural and other social functions; depending on specific historical conditions, the age criteria for young people can vary from 16 to 30 years old" [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The specificity of the social status of young people as a social group is manifested in the fact that this group of "incomplete" entry into society, characterized by an intermediate position "between childhood and adulthood." The young person no longer plays the role of a child and at the same time is not a full-fledged bearer of the roles of adults. Youth as an age group is characterized by a specific lifestyle, behavioral style, cultural norms and values. Describing the way of life of youth, it is expedient to refer to the concept of "youth", which is synonymous with the concept of "youth", the use of which focuses on the meaning of beginning, freshness, flourishing. Youth is a special feeling of the world, oneself, aspiration for the future, optimism, love of life, thirst for activity. Youth is one of the states of the soul inherent in every person, which manifests itself in spontaneous behavior, in immediacy, non-standard reactions.

Youth as a time of beginning is associated in consciousness with the future, prospects, hopes, therefore, it shows more a certain aspiration (intention) than certain characteristics. For example, this is manifested in the definitions "young specialist", "young father", "young

worker”, which serve more as a promise to take place than they show a specific result. At the same time, this life period is often full of stress, problems, conflicts with oneself and society. Youth in social terms is clearly associated with a set of social tasks, roles and statuses. These include, in particular, getting an education, starting a professional activity, choosing a life partner and building your own family. This is a key period of transition between the dependent and weak period of childhood and the independent, autonomous and very strong stage of adulthood. If childhood is more associated with schooling, and adult life - with professional (labor) employment, then youth as a period is between these social spheres; it is the end of compulsory secondary education and the beginning of labor activity. If childhood is spent in the family of origin, and adult life is connected with building one's own family and having children, then youth is the stage of transition between them. These two main points of transformation are the main tasks of development in the youth group. And it is the solution of these two tasks that characterizes youth as an age group [2; 4].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the history of childhood and the history of youth are two intertwined trajectories, connected in one line in medieval times and more and more branching with the advent of the era of industrialization. By the end of the XX century. youth, as a transitional stage of the life cycle, was characterized by a semi-dependent status both in terms of leaving the parental family and professionally.

Middle and last quarter of the 20th century. brought significant changes in the social context and social organization of youth as a transitional period from childhood to adulthood. 1960-80s were characterized as the time of emergence and flourishing of the youth subculture. During this time, many scientists of various fields noted that age is gradually turning into one of the dominant coordinates of social differentiation and social discrimination. The youth subcultures of that time clearly showed signs of social differentiation, which was based only on age. Age has become a substitute for class as the main basis of social stratification.

Thus, youth as an age group is characterized by a special way of life, social status and role expectations, as well as a place and functions in the modern social system, which have a historical and cultural conditionality and are associated with key characteristics youth as a special stage in life.

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